

Polarographic Studies on the Influence of the Concentration and Nature of Different Supporting Electrolytes on the Kinetics of the Irreversible Electrode Processes of Ni(II) and Co(II)

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The polarographic behaviour of Ni(II) and Co(II) has been studied in different supporting electrolytes of varying concentrations. On applying various criteria of ascertaining the irreversible nature of the polarographic reductions, it has been found that the reduction of Ni(II) and Co(II) is totally irreversible. Kouteckys treatment has been applied to calculate the rate constant $k_{f,h}$ at various potentials along the course of a polarogram in the presence of different concentrations of the supporting electrolytes. The values of the kinetic parameters ($k_{f,h}^0$ and αn_a) and also of $\Delta G^\ddagger$, the free energy of activation, have been obtained at different concentrations of the supporting electrolytes. A quantitative interpretation in terms of the values of kinetic parameters has been put forward to explain the influence of the concentration and nature of the supporting electrolytes.

MUKHERJEE and Chakravarti¹; Nath and Bhattacharya² have studied the effect of the nature and concentration of some supporting electrolytes on $E_{1/2}$ and i_d values of Ni(II) and Co(II). However, polarographic studies on the effect of the nature and concentration of supporting electrolytes on the kinetics of the electrode processes of Ni(II) and Co(II) are still incomprehensive. With this aim in view the present study on the polarographic behavior of Ni(II) and Co(II) in different concentrations of a number of supporting electrolytes has been undertaken. The rate constant, $k_{f,h}$ at different applied potentials has been calculated using Koutecky's treatment³. The values of the kinetic parameters, ' αn_a ' and $k_{f,h}^0$ and also of $\Delta G^\ddagger$ have been calculated (Fig. 1 and 2).

Fig. 1. Log $k_{f,h}$ vs. $E_{d.e.}$ plots for Ni(II) at different concentrations of some supporting electrolytes
A - Plots for KNO_3
B - Plots for NH_4Cl
- O - M/20
- x - M/10
- Δ - M/2
- $\bullet$ - M

Fig. 2. Log $k_{f,h}$ vs. $E_{d.e.}$ plots for Co(II) at different concentrations of some supporting electrolytes.
A - Plots for NaCl
B - Plots for $NaNO_3$
- O - M/20
- x - M/10
- Δ - M/2
- $\bullet$ - M

Experimental

$Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and $Co(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ were of A.R., B.D.H. grade and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The supporting electrolytes used were either A.R. B.D.H. or E. Merck, G.R. products. The resultant concentrations of Ni(II) and Co(II) were maintained at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ in each case.

A manual polarograph (Toshniwal, CLO2) in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal, PL50) was used. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 0.1 M KNO_3 , open circuit):

$$\begin{aligned} h_{orr} &= 61.37 \text{ cm} \\ t &= 3.10 \text{ sec.} \\ m^{2/3} t^{1/6} &= 1.983 \text{ mg}^{1/3} \text{ sec.}^{-1/6} \end{aligned}$$

All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Purified hydrogen was used for removing dissolved oxygen. Triton X-100 (0.002%) was used as the maxima suppressor.

Throughout the measurements, the current at the end of the drop life was recorded instead of the average because the determination of kinetic parameters is based on Koutecky's² calculations which are more accurately reproduced by measuring the maximum current⁴.

Results and Discussion

The reduction of Ni(II) and Co(II) has been found to be diffusion-controlled at all concentrations of the supporting electrolytes as revealed by the linearity of i_a vs $\sqrt{h}$ plots.

Irreversibility tests: Various criteria of ascertaining the irreversibility of the polarographic reduction of Ni(II) and Co(II) in different supporting electrolytes of varying concentrations, have been applied. The following results are obtained:

(i) The values of slopes of 'log plots' are of the order of 0.10 V. These are much larger than the theoretical values expected for a two electron reduction process of Ni(II) and Co(II). From this it follows that the polarographic reduction of Ni(II) and Co(II) is irreversible in all concentrations of the supporting electrolytes used. The same conclusion is derived from ' $E_{\frac{3}{4}} - E_{\frac{1}{4}}$ ' values.

(ii) Values of ' α ':

From the relation ' $E_{\frac{3}{4}} - E_{\frac{1}{4}} = 0.0564 \alpha n$ ', the value of ' $E_{\frac{3}{4}} - E_{\frac{1}{4}}$ ' can be used to prove that a process is totally irreversible⁶ if $\alpha < 0.5$. Taking $n=2$ for Ni(II) and Co(II) the values were calculated and it has been found that α is less than 0.5 in all cases thereby showing that the polarographic reduction of Ni(II) and Co(II) is totally irreversible.

(iii) Effect of the pressure head of mercury:

The theory of irreversible waves⁷ demands that the current being kinetically controlled is independent of the pressure head of mercury at the foot of the wave and becomes diffusion-controlled at the top, varying linearly with $h^{\frac{1}{2}}$. This dependence of the current on 'h' at different stages of the wave is studied by plotting $(h/h_0)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs. $(i/i_0)_m$ where current $(i_0)_m$ corresponds to lowest mercury head (h_0). The subscript 'm' denotes the condition pertaining to the instant before the drop becomes just disconnected⁸. These plots are given in Figs. 3 and 4. From these figures it is clear that the current corresponding to the foot of the wave is independent of the mercury head whereas at the top of the wave (i.e., at the

Fig. 3. Effect of variation of mercury pressure head on maximum current at various stages in the reduction wave of Ni(II) in the presence of 0.1 M NH_4Br . Plots I, II, III, IV and V correspond to potentials, -1.02, -1.08, -1.10, 1.14 and -1.28 V (vs. S.C.E.).

Fig. 4. Effect of variation of mercury pressure head on maximum current at various stages in the reduction wave of Co(II) in the presence of 0.1 M KNO_3 . Plots I, II, III, IV and V correspond to potentials, -1.20, -1.26, -1.28, -1.30 and V -1.34 (vs. S.C.E.).

limiting current value) it is proportional to $h^{\frac{1}{2}}$. In between the two extremes both the rate of the electron transfer and the diffusion determine the magnitude of the current.

This transient dependence of the current on the mercury head has also been studied in terms of $\log i$ vs. $\log h$ plots. These plots have been depicted in figs. 5 and 6. From these figures it is evident that the slope of 'log-log' plot is zero at the potential corresponding to the foot of the wave and it gradually increases to 0.5 as the potential corresponding to the limiting current is reached and in between the two extremes the slope varies from 0 to 0.5. This confirms that while the current is totally kinetically controlled at the foot of the wave it

TABLE-1. VALUES OF KINETIC PARAMETERS (αn_a AND $k_{f,h}^{\circ}$) AND OF $\Delta G^{\ddagger}$, FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTION OF Ni(II) IN THE PRESENCE OF VARYING CONCENTRATIONS OF DIFFERENT SUPPORTING ELECTROLYTES.

Concn. of supporting electrolytes	αn_a	$\Delta G^{\ddagger}$ k.cal.	$k_{f,h}^{\circ}$ cm./sec
NaCl			
M/20	0.6775	31.521	2.27×10^{-13}
M/10	0.5962	29.160	2.62×10^{-13}
M/2	0.3657	24.917	1.98×10^{-9}
M	0.2981	25.114	9.66×10^{-9}
NaNO ₃			
M/20	0.5962	29.017	3.53×10^{-12}
M/10	0.5653	30.985	7.89×10^{-13}
M/2	0.4608	30.259	3.03×10^{-14}
M	0.4471	29.017	7.01×10^{-14}
NaClO ₄			
M/20	0.5962	30.657	4.02×10^{-12}
M/10	0.5962	30.726	3.92×10^{-13}
M/2	0.5152	28.702	3.67×10^{-11}
M	0.4608	26.621	1.25×10^{-10}
KCl			
M/20	0.5693	28.867	9.77×10^{-13}
M/10	0.4704	26.401	1.78×10^{-10}
M/2	0.4410	26.000	2.24×10^{-11}
M	0.4066	25.500	8.18×10^{-10}
KNO ₃			
M/20	0.6528	27.691	7.73×10^{-13}
M/10	0.5948	26.958	4.80×10^{-13}
M/2	0.5451	26.000	5.50×10^{-12}
M	0.5393	24.915	3.74×10^{-12}
NH ₄ Cl			
M/20	0.5018	28.990	1.94×10^{-13}
M/10	0.4878	28.792	4.56×10^{-13}
M/2	0.4771	28.441	1.17×10^{-12}
M	0.4746	28.167	1.66×10^{-11}
NH ₄ Br			
M/20	0.5420	27.203	3.35×10^{-11}
M/10	0.5420	28.167	1.69×10^{-10}
M/2	0.5161	29.440	7.76×10^{-13}
M	0.5161	31.144	6.80×10^{-14}
NH ₄ I			
M/20	0.6103	29.986	6.44×10^{-13}
M/10	0.5420	30.536	4.65×10^{-13}
M/2	0.4878	31.371	1.37×10^{-11}
NH ₄ NO ₃			
M/20	0.5962	29.017	1.68×10^{-13}
M/10	0.5834	28.672	1.46×10^{-12}
M/2	0.5705	28.326	1.03×10^{-12}
M	0.5420	28.031	6.13×10^{-13}
CH ₃ COONH ₄			
M/20	0.5420	30.902	4.78×10^{-12}
M/10	0.5340	31.447	4.01×10^{-13}
M/2	0.5300	31.722	2.63×10^{-12}
M	0.5132	31.995	3.98×10^{-13}
Mg(NO ₃) ₂			
M/20	0.5693	28.851	2.59×10^{-12}
M/10	0.5355	29.000	5.33×10^{-13}
M/2	0.5287	30.511	4.83×10^{-13}
M	0.5084	31.230	1.42×10^{-11}
Ca(NO ₃) ₂			
M/20	0.5420	28.980	8.30×10^{-13}
M/10	0.4813	29.124	6.16×10^{-12}
M/2	0.4608	29.398	2.95×10^{-11}
M	0.3947	30.081	1.60×10^{-10}
Sr(NO ₃) ₂			
M/20	0.4471	29.124	2.76×10^{-11}
M/10	0.4406	29.534	6.27×10^{-11}
M/2	0.4066	30.081	1.39×10^{-10}
M	0.3930	30.355	1.20×10^{-10}
Ba(NO ₃) ₂			
M/20	0.5147	29.398	2.31×10^{-12}
M/15	0.4878	29.808	2.06×10^{-12}
M/10	0.4810	30.628	9.80×10^{-11}
M/5	0.4066	31.175	6.84×10^{-10}

TABLE—2 VALUES OF KINETIC PARAMETERS (αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$) and of $\Delta G_{\ddagger}$ FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTION OF Co(II) IN THE PRESENCE OF VARYING CONCENTRATIONS OF DIFFERENT SUPPORTING ELECTROLYTES.

Concn. of supporting electrolytes	αn_a	$\Delta G_{\ddagger}$ k.cal.	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm./sec
		NaCl	
M/20	0.5846	32.1791	4.01×10^{-13}
M/10	0.5480	31.7232	6.15×10^{-13}
M/2	0.4570	26.2273	2.53×10^{-13}
M	0.4353	26.5735	9.31×10^{-13}
		NaNO ₃	
M/20	0.5488	31.3800	2.91×10^{-13}
M/10	0.5084	30.7756	5.70×10^{-13}
M/2	0.4406	29.5410	2.56×10^{-13}
M	0.3387	24.9276	2.88×10^{-13}
		NaClO ₄	
M/20	0.5990	32.2300	3.95×10^{-13}
M/10	0.5553	31.2900	1.37×10^{-13}
M/2	0.4878	31.4000	6.22×10^{-13}
M	0.4460	30.8300	1.08×10^{-13}
		KCl	
M/20	0.5615	31.7727	6.42×10^{-13}
M/10	0.4652	29.6137	1.52×10^{-13}
M/2	0.4367	29.1400	1.72×10^{-13}
M	0.4241	29.0564	1.57×10^{-11}
		KNO ₃	
M/20	0.5262	32.1161	6.63×10^{-13}
M/10	0.4628	30.3661	6.95×10^{-13}
M/2	0.4554	29.1620	1.95×10^{-11}
M	0.4413	28.8100	1.37×10^{-13}
		NH ₄ Cl	
M/20	0.5553	31.4363	1.07×10^{-13}
M/10	0.5425	30.2200	7.40×10^{-13}
M/2	0.4217	28.9000	2.24×10^{-11}
M	0.3625	27.4705	1.45×10^{-10}

TABLE—3. $k_{f,h}$ VALUES AT SELECTED POTENTIALS FOR DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF THE SUPPORTING ELECTROLYTES.

Supporting electrolyte	Concentration of supporting electrolyte	Ni(II)	Co(II)
		$k_{f,h} \times 10^3$ cm/sec (at -1.12 V, S.C.E.)	$k_{f,h} \times 10^3$ cm/sec (at -1.30 V, S.C.E.)
NaCl	M/20	1.6702	-
	M/10	1.3980	3.8906
	M/2	0.5245	0.5787
	M	0.3890	-
NaNO ₃	M/20	2.5565	1.9568
	M/10	1.6302	0.9387
	M/2	0.6406	-
	M	0.3882	-
NaClO ₄	M/20	-	1.7109
	M/10	2.0500	1.3732
	M/2	-	0.4912
	M	0.9424	-
KCl	M/20	2.1858	-
	M/10	1.6386	-
	M/2	-	1.4742
	M	-	0.7905
KNO ₃	M/20	3.6450	3.0080
	M/10	2.6378	1.2130
	M/2	0.7485	-
	M	0.6421	-
NH ₄ NO ₃	M/20	1.1913	-
	M/10	0.6912	-
	M/2	0.2743	-
	M	0.1516	-
NH ₄ Cl	M/20	2.1098	5.7100
	M/10	1.5540	1.5523
	M/2	0.6237	1.0263
	M	0.2108	0.4976
NH ₄ Br	M/20	3.5678	-
	M/10	1.7380	-
	M/2	1.0420	-
	M	0.5076	-

Table-3. (Contd.)

NH ₄ I	M/20	1.1200	-
	M/10	0.8743	-
	M/2	0.5230	-
Mg(NO ₃) ₂	M/20	0.7856	-
	M/10	0.4016	-
	M/2	0.2540	-
	M	-	-
Ca(NO ₃) ₂	M/20	0.9064	-
	M/10	0.8710	-
	M/2	0.2448	-
	M	0.1060	-
Sr(NO ₃) ₂	M/20	0.3020	-
	M/10	0.2524	-
	M/2	0.1215	-
	M	0.0717	-
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	M/20	0.3235	-
	M/15	0.3146	-
	M/10	0.2786	-
	M/5	0.0372	-

becomes diffusion-controlled at the top and in between the two extremes both the rate of electron transfer and the diffusion determine the magnitude of the current.

Fig. 5. Log-Log plots for Ni(II) in the presence of 0.1 M NaCl. Plots I, II, III, IV, V, VI and VII correspond to potentials, -1.00, -1.02, -1.04, -1.08, -1.10, -1.12 and -1.14 V (vs S. C. E.).

Effect of the concentration and the nature of the supporting electrolytes on kinetic parameters :

(i) ' αn_a ' values : The product ' αn_a ' records a decrease with increase in the concentration of supporting electrolytes (Tables 1 & 2). The polarographic reduction of Ni(II) and Co(II) is a well established 2 electron process and therefore ' n_a ', the number of electrons involved in the rate determining step, can either be 1 or 2. Since the decrease in ' αn_a ' values is indiscrete and at no stage the two consecutive values vary by a factor of 2, the possibility of decrease in the value of the product ' αn_a ' due to a change in ' n_a ' may be ruled out. Thus, it may be safely concluded that it is ' α ' which is decreasing. ' α ', the transfer coefficient signifies⁹ the fraction of the applied voltage which favours the cathodic

Fig. 6. Log-Log plots for Co(II) in the presence of 0.1 M NaCl. Plots I, II, III, IV, V, VI, VII and VIII correspond to potentials, -1.10, -1.12, -1.14, -1.16, -1.18, -1.20, -1.24 and -1.26 V (vs. S. C. E.).

reaction, $M^{n+} + ne \rightarrow M$ (where M stands for Ni or Co). A decrease in the value of ' α ' thus implies that the transfer of electron/electrons is made increasingly difficult. In other words the electrode reaction is rendered increasingly more irreversible. The shift in $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ to more negative potentials and increase in slope values of log plots and ' $E_{\frac{3}{2}} - E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ ' values lend support to the above conclusion. These conclusions are further borne out by the observation of Jha and Srivastava¹⁰.

(ii) $k_{f,h}^0$ values : The value of potential dependent heterogeneous rate constant $k_{f,h}$ at the formal potential of the O-R (oxidant-reductant) couple in the solution is denoted by $k_{s,h}$ and is called the standard rate constant. Since the formal potentials for many totally irreversible couples are unknown or even unmeasurable, a more convenient choice is 0 V (zero volt) vs. N.H.E. (-0.2412 V vs. S.C.E.). Here the value of $k_{f,h}$ is denoted by $k_{f,h}^0$. Yet the fact remains that it is the value of $k_{s,h}$ that determines whether a

half-reaction is reversible or irreversible. If it exceeds about 2×10^{-2} cm. sec., the couple would appear polarographically reversible. But if $k_{s,h}$ is smaller than about 3×10^{-5} cm./sec., the couple would be totally irreversible.

Though $k_{s,h}$ is more useful for describing the behaviour of a particular couple, it is $k^0_{f,h}$ that is more useful for comparing the behaviour of different totally irreversible couples¹¹. Since the formal potentials of Ni²⁺/Ni and Co²⁺/Co couples in different concentrations of the supporting electrolytes used in the present study are not known, the values of $k^0_{f,h}$ have been calculated from the polarographic data of Ni(II) and Co(II) in the presence of different supporting electrolytes of varying concentrations and are listed in Tables 1 and 2.

Though the values of $k^0_{f,h}$ obtained for the polarographic reduction of Ni(II) and Co(II) in the presence of varying concentrations of supporting electrolytes are of the same order of magnitude as reported¹²⁻¹⁷ for totally irreversible electrode processes yet the fact remains that there is no regularity in the variation of its values with the change in the concentration of the supporting electrolytes. Meites¹⁸ has also hinted at this limitation of $k^0_{f,h}$ in interpreting the results. However, the effect of the change of the concentration of the supporting electrolyte on the rate of electrode reaction can be studied in terms of the values of $k_{f,h}$ at a suitable potential. This potential should be such as to lie in between the potentials corresponding to the foot and the top of the polarographic wave since at such a potential both the rate of electron-transfer and the diffusion determine the magnitude of the current. For Ni(II) this potential has been chosen as -1.12 V (vs. S.C.E.) and for Co(II) as -1.30 V (vs. S.C.E.) and the values of $k_{f,h}$ at these potentials have been presented in table 3. From this Table it is evident that the value of $k_{f,h}$ decreases as the concentration of the supporting electrolyte increases. This observation is in harmony with the conclusions derived on the basis of ' αn_a ' values.

The nature of the supporting electrolyte may also play a significant role in affecting the values of ' αn_a ' and $k^0_{f,h}$. This study was undertaken by choosing the supporting electrolytes in such a way so as to keep the anion of the supporting electrolytes the same while changing the cations and vice-versa. A perusal of the Table 1 and 2 shows that for both the cases, i.e., the supporting electrolytes where cation is changed keeping anion identical and vice-versa, the magnitude of the variation of ' αn_a ' and $k^0_{f,h}$ from lowest concentration to the highest concentration (of the supporting electrolyte) is not identical for different supporting electrolytes used. Since Mukherjee and Chakravarti (loc. cit.) and Nath and Bhattacharya (loc. cit.) while studying the influence of the nature and concentration of the supporting electrolytes on the polarographic characteristics of Ni(II) and Co(II) have maintained that various factors such as ionic strength, interionic forces, viscosity, overvoltage and adsorption play a

significant role, no generalisation with respect to the influence of the nature of anions and cations of the supporting electrolytes on the kinetic parameters can be contemplated.

$\Delta G^\ddagger$ values: The values of $\Delta G^\ddagger$, the free energy of activation at different concentrations of the supporting electrolytes have been presented in Table 1 and 2. It is interesting to note that the values of $\Delta G^\ddagger$ in almost all cases lie between 25 k. cal. and 31 k. cal. It is worthwhile to mention here that Strassner and Delahay⁵ have reported a value of $\Delta G^\ddagger$ equal to 24.1 k. cal. for the electro-reduction of Ni(II) ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) in KNO_3 (M) in the presence of 0.001% gelatin. A close agreement between the $\Delta G^\ddagger$ values calculated for different supporting electrolytes of the present study and the observation of Strassner and Delahay (loc. cit.) signifies that the value of the order of 25 to 30 k. cal. characterises the irreversible polarographic reduction of Ni(II) and Co(II).

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